

A Study on Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana and Its Role in Fostering Financial Inclusion in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Kalaiarasan, G. "A Study on Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana and Its Role in Fostering Financial Inclusion in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 156–60.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412552>

G.Kalaiarasan

*Final Year B.Com (Corporate Secretaryship) Student – Loyola College
Company Secretaryship - Executive*

Poverty is the deprivation of opportunity - Amartya Sen

Abstract

India has always been a booming market for the financial activities of both commercial banks and the public sector banks. But have all sects of the Indian society been able to access these financial services? With the liberalization policy embarked by the government in 1991, private banks started to emerge out and the already existing public sector banks started to spread its services to reach out to every part of the society. All these efforts helped significantly to remove the myth of banks being a place only for the rich and business class people from the minds of commoners. But however, such myths were so deep-rooted that its traces can still seem to exist in the society in a very subtle manner. Financial inclusion is a key matter of concern in our country to achieve a socio-economic development. The government from its side initiated several schemes to achieve financial inclusion in India, but however, not all efforts of the government seemed to be fruitful. For instance, the Swabhimaan scheme introduced ended as an utter failure. To ensure financial inclusion in India, our Honorable Prime Minister Dr. Narendra Modi launched the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) on 15 August 2014. Since its initiation, the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana has performed significantly to achieve its purpose. This research paper is an attempt to study about the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana program and its role in ensuring financial inclusion in India. This paper includes a survey which was conducted by the researcher with the residents of a slum called Thideer Nagar located in Chennai to understand the impact created by the program in their area. Also, the data collected from the archives of the official website of the initiative has been summarized and interpreted to study the scenario of financial inclusion in India after the implementation of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, No-frills account, Formal financial sector and Informal financial sector, Socio-economic development.

Introduction

The Government of India launched the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana on 15 August 2014 to ensure financial inclusion in India. This scheme is applicable to people in the age group of 20 to 65. This scheme was launched with an aim to expand and make affordable access to financial services such as bank accounts, remittances, credit, insurance and pensions. Ever since its initiation, this scheme has

enjoyed a wide reach and participation especially, in the rural areas. Benefits of the scheme include opening of no-frills accounts, relaxation on know-your-customer (KYC) norms and direct benefit transfer such as direct transfer of government subsidies to the beneficiary's account. This reduces delay and leakage to get service.

Objectives of Study

1. To understand the concept of financial inclusion and its importance.
2. To study about the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana program and its role in ensuring financial inclusion in India.
3. To study the impact created by Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana on the residents of the chosen place (Thideer Nagar).
4. To analyze the effectiveness of the program based upon the data collected from the archives of the government.

A Survey with the Residents of Thideer Nagar

A survey was conducted with the residents of a slum area called “Thideer Nagar” in Chennai. The idea behind conducting this survey is to study the impact created by the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana in their locality. With poor standards of living, slums are the most financially excluded places in India. Hence, conducting the survey in this area helped greatly in getting a clear picture about the implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana and thus this place and the people residing here best suited the purpose of this survey.

Research Methodology

The survey had a total number of 156 respondents. Out of the 156 respondents, 90 of them were men and the rest were women. This survey was conducted only with those people who belonged to the age group 20-65, as this scheme is applicable to only those who belonged to this particular age group. Random sampling method was used for this survey. The data collected was analyzed using the percentage analysis method.

Analysis and Interpretation

The respondents had showed great eager and enthusiasm in responding to the questionnaire provided to them. The following are the interpretations drawn from the percentage analysis of responses to the questionnaire:

1. Are you aware of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana?

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana seemed to be quiet popular in this locality just like it is in the rest of the nation, as 78% of the respondents were aware of this scheme. The wide scale advertising of the scheme led its wide reach.

2. Have you opened any bank account under the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana scheme?

This locality had shown good participation towards the scheme as around 70% of the respondents had opened a bank account under the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana scheme. Also, the respondents felt that opening a bank account now has become a lot easier than the normal process prior to this scheme. The people are now relieved from the cumbersome process which prevailed earlier.

3. Before the introduction of the scheme, whom did you rely on to meet your financial needs?

Before the introduction of the scheme, more than 70% of the respondents relied on the informal financial sector to meet their financial needs. Most of the respondents also admitted that usury was commonly practiced in their locality and most of them were even victims of it. Since, the residents of this area did not have access to the banking services they often had to rely on such informal sources of credit even though it had high interest rates in order to meet their financial needs.

4. Do you maintain zero balance in your bank account

Bank account holders under the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana scheme have the option to maintain zero balance in their accounts. This bar graph however shows that only a meager number of 7% of the respondents have been maintaining zero balance in their bank account.

5. How often do you use your bank account?

The main idea behind this initiative was not just to ensure everyone had opened bank account, but to make them use it actively, as simply opening a bank account wouldn't constitute meaningful financial inclusion. This representation shows that more than 60% of the respondents use their bank accounts often and some of them even use it almost daily.

Findings from the Survey

The main motive of conducting this survey was to study the impact created by Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana in the lives of these people. On analyzing the responses to the questionnaire, it is clearly evident that this scheme has created a huge impact in the day-to-day lives of these people. Earlier to the introduction of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana only a paltry number of people had bank accounts in this slum. However, now a majority of them here have a bank account and it is also used quite often by them. The residents of this slum are now relieved from the high interest charged by the loan sharks for their loans as they can now get loans at cheaper rates from the banks. Also, these people can now directly avail the government subsidies as it can now be transferred directly to their accounts. Apart from opening bank accounts, people in this slum have also now started to deposit their savings in bank accounts, which also fetches them a certain amount of income in form of interest. This place and these people thus stand as a fine example of a financially inclusive India. Thus, it can be concluded that the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana has created a huge impact in the lives of these people.

Summary of the Data of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana

The following is the summary of the data about the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana that has been provided by government at <https://pmjdy.gov.in/Archive>. More than 36 crore accounts were opened under the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) since its implementation and over 80 per cent of these are active accounts. Over 15 million bank accounts were opened on the inauguration day alone. Both public sector banks and private sector banks have contributed enormously to this scheme. However, the contributions of the public sector banks to this scheme has been more significant than the contributions of the private sector banks, as over 80 percent of the bank accounts opened under this scheme were opened in public sector banks. The PMJDY covered all the 29 states and 7 union territories in India, of which it was most successfully implemented in Chhattisgarh. Women had showed more enthusiastic participation than men, as 53% of the accounts opened were by women. Although in the initial years of the scheme, the number of zero balance maintained accounts were huge, the data suggests that in the later years, such numbers came down drastically. The data also suggests that the participation in rural areas is more than that of in urban areas, as around 60 percent of the accounts were opened in the rural places. Thus, with these data it can be concluded that the scheme had been a huge success all throughout the country although, certain variations can be found in relative comparison of one place to another.

Conclusion

For the past three decades, developing countries all around the world have placed greater emphasis on financial inclusion as research findings correlate the direct link between the financial exclusion and the poverty prevailing in developing nations. The initiation of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana in India has been a milestone step in fostering financial inclusion in India. Despite the initiative being politicized much, the initiative had still managed to serve the purpose behind its initiation effectively. Unlike the previous financial inclusion programs which lacked proper implementation, the government has given greater importance to the efficient implementation of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, which has been the key reason for the scheme's success. On the whole it can be concluded that the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana has made a huge impact in the lives of the unbanked sects of society, which is now transforming them into a financially literate and responsible citizens of India.

Bibliography

1. <https://pmjdy.gov.in/>
2. <https://pmjdy.gov.in/Archive>.
3. <https://www.rbi.org.in/>
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pradhan_Mantri_Jan_Dhan_Yojana.